

ADDITIVE MANUFACTURING SOLUTIONS FOR SOLAR THERMAL PROPULSION: AN INTEGRATED CORE DESIGN APPROACH

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ABSTRACT: In Solar Thermal Propulsion, a high-temperature Receiver-Absorber Cavity (RAC) converts concentrated sunlight into heat, which is then transferred to a propellant and expanded through a nozzle to generate thrust. Conventional RACs are often limited by material coupling issues, such as thermal expansion mismatches, material degradation, and restricted geometric freedom, leading to inefficiencies or failure under the demanding operating temperatures involved. This work presents a comprehensive approach to the design and manufacturing of a Solar Thermal Thruster (STT) core that integrates the RAC Thermal Energy Storage (TES) capability and the Heat Exchanger (HEX) into a single component, enabled by advancements in Additive Manufacturing (AM) for high-temperature applications.

1. INTRODUCTION

Solar Thermal Propulsion (STP) has been studied since the 1960s as a promising combustion-free space propulsion solution. Several studies have identified STP as a candidate for main engine applications in orbital transfer vehicles, due to its performance lying between chemical and electric engines [1], [2]. In particular, a Solar Thermal Thruster (STT) can provide relatively high specific impulse, thanks to the use of low molecular weight propellants and high temperatures, while maintaining higher thrust levels than classic electric solutions.

The case study and requirements used in this work are driven by the EU–EIC Pathfinder project Green Solar-to-Propellant Water Propulsion (Green SWaP), which is developing a bimodal propulsion system that uses solar energy to convert water into propellant. The project aims to demonstrate a propulsion architecture combining a 200 N chemical thruster based on a hydrogen–hydrogen peroxide mixture and a 1 N thrust STT using hydrogen as propellant [3]. The latter, designed to achieve specific impulses up to 500 s, is intended for Reaction Control System (RCS) applications and will be the main objective of this work. A preliminary mission analysis selected the application scenario for this bimodal propulsion system and derived system and subsystem requirements

for the conversion, concentration, and propulsion technologies. The outcome of this study was a dual-system architecture comprising a refuelling station with conversion capabilities, orbiting at 700 km in a Sun-synchronous Low Earth Orbit (LEO), and a reusable kick stage that provides precise orbit injection for payloads up to 500 kg. All the details are described in [4], while in the next section, the impact of the mission analysis results on the STT design will be discussed.

The operating temperature range for these systems imposes stringent constraints on material selection, structural integrity, and thermal management. Moreover, overall system performances are strongly governed by the heat transfer efficiency between the receiver and the propellant, which depends on both material properties and manufacturing capabilities. Additive Manufacturing (AM), combined with advances in high-temperature materials, offers new opportunities to address these challenges. AM enables the realisation of complex geometries, such as Triply Periodic Minimal Surface (TPMS) lattices [5], which can enhance heat transfer while reducing mass and pressure losses [6]. Furthermore, the integration of multiple functions into a single monolithic component reduces interfaces and enables more efficient and robust designs. However, the Thermal Energy Storage (TES) and Heat Exchanger (HEX) functionalities impose competing requirements: the TES must ensure thermal storage capacity and resistance to cyclic loading, whereas the HEX must maximize surface area and promote uniform hydrogen flow under steep thermal gradients. Their integration into a single architecture therefore represents a key design challenge.

This work addresses this challenge by first defining the system requirements and identifying candidate materials suitable for TES applications and compatible with AM. These include refractory metals (e.g., tungsten and molybdenum alloys), high-temperature ceramics (e.g., silicon carbide and boron carbide), and carbon-based materials, evaluated in terms of TES performance, hydrogen compatibility, and manufacturability. A design methodology is then introduced to determine the main engine parameters, which are used to size the absorber, cavity, and HEX. Finally, the impact of AM-enabled design freedom is investigated through the development and comparison of two HEX configurations: a conventional helical

design and a TPMS-based architecture. Numerical simulations are employed to assess their thermal performance and to quantify the benefits of lattice-based solutions in terms of heat transfer and overall system efficiency.

2. REQUIREMENTS

A STT core consists of a Receiver–Absorber Cavity (RAC) system coupled with a HEX, surrounded by thermal insulation and connected downstream to a plenum and nozzle for propellant expansion. The core design is primarily driven by the heating strategy and the propulsion mode.

Two main heating approaches can be identified: direct and indirect [7]. In direct heating, the propellant is heated through direct absorption of solar radiation, typically by seeding it with radiation-absorbing particles or species. This approach requires a transparent window to confine the propellant while allowing radiation to enter the system. In contrast, indirect heating relies on a solid absorber that captures solar radiation and dissipates it as thermal energy, which is transferred to the propellant through radiation and conduction. In this configuration, a window is only required if specific solutions such as transpiration cooling are adopted; otherwise, a cavity–absorber system is sufficient. The indirect approach is adopted in this study, as it naturally enables the integration of the absorber and HEX into a single radiative system, consistent with a monolithic design enabled by AM.

The propulsion mode can similarly be categorised into direct heating operation and TES-based operation. In direct operation, thrust can only be generated under sunlight conditions, as the propellant is heated instantaneously. In contrast, a TES-based system stores thermal energy during sunlit phases and releases it on demand, enabling operation during eclipses. Although no explicit requirement is defined within the Green SWaP framework, the intended use of the thruster for RCS applications strongly favours the TES approach. RCS operation requires immediate and continuous availability, which cannot be guaranteed with direct heating alone, particularly in LEO, where eclipse periods occur approximately every 90 minutes and can last up to 30 minutes. For this reason, a TES-based architecture is selected as the baseline for all subsequent design work.

The adoption of TES significantly impacts system design. Compared to direct heating, larger thermal masses must be heated, leading to increased power requirements and, consequently, larger solar concentrators. The achievable operating temperature is determined by the balance between incoming solar power and thermal losses, primarily due to radiation. While an ideal adiabatic system would exhibit continuous temperature increase, real systems reach an equilibrium temperature that depends on surface emissivity and insulation performance. Thermal losses can be mitigated by reducing surface emissivity through coatings, and by limiting the external surface temperature via low-conductivity insulation

layers.

These requirements introduce a fundamental trade-off in the design of a monolithic core. The TES function benefits from high thermal conductivity to ensure uniform heat distribution and avoid local overheating, while effective insulation requires low thermal conductivity to minimize heat losses to the environment. Reconciling these competing requirements within a single-material or integrated structure represents a key design challenge.

On the other hand, AM offers significant advantages in manufacturing. Traditional designs often rely on multiple materials and interfaces, which introduce risks related to thermal expansion mismatch and poor thermal contact. The integration of the HEX within the core—potentially even at intermediate radial positions—would be difficult to achieve with conventional manufacturing due to these constraints. In contrast, AM enables the realization of monolithic architectures with complex internal geometries, allowing greater flexibility in HEX placement and potentially improving heat transfer uniformity and TES discharge behaviour.

The operating temperature and nominal mass flow rate are two further parameters that strongly affect the STT design and the manufacturing strategy. The specific impulse I_{sp} of a STT is related to the effective exhaust velocity v_e through the gravitational constant as a scale factor. For an ideal isentropic expansion, v_e depends on the chamber stagnation temperature T_c and the propellant molecular weight M : for a fixed nozzle geometry and pressure ratio, I_{sp} scales with the square root of the T_c/M ratio, so raising the propellant temperature and reducing its molecular weight are the most direct levers for improving performance. In this work, the specific heat of hydrogen and the ratio of specific heats γ were treated as temperature-averaged constants, computed using the CEA tool [8] at inlet, throat, and outlet conditions. Based on classical rocket theory [9], achieving the target specific impulse of 500 s in vacuum requires chamber temperatures in the range $T_c = 800\text{--}1200$ K, where the boundaries are set to reach specific impulse in the range of $\pm 10\%$ with respect to the nominal value. Reaching these temperatures requires concentrating solar radiation through a parabolic reflector, with the receiver and HEX exposed to temperatures approaching 1500 K in the worst-case scenario. For a target thrust of $F = 1$ N at a chamber pressure of $p_c = 5$ bar, the corresponding propellant mass flow rate falls in the range $\dot{m}_p = 0.17\text{--}0.23$ g s⁻¹, reflecting a $\pm 15\%$ band around the nominal operating point of 0.20 g s⁻¹.

3. CANDIDATE MATERIALS

The selection of a material for the integrated RAC core is particularly challenging, as it must simultaneously satisfy structural, thermal, and chemical requirements while remaining compatible with hydrogen propellant at high temperatures and AM processes. In addition to withstanding operating temper-

atures, the material must endure repeated thermal cycling typical of LEO missions (see Figure 5) and, in the case of a TES-based architecture, provide sufficient thermal storage capacity. These requirements are further complicated by the need to balance high thermal conductivity, which promotes uniform temperature distribution and efficient heat exchange, with low thermal conductivity of outer layers, which is desirable for thermal insulation. At the same time, AM maturity depends strongly on the material used.

Candidate materials for this temperature regime include refractory metals (e.g., tungsten and molybdenum), high-temperature ceramics (e.g., silicon carbide and alumina), and carbon-based materials (e.g., graphite and carbon-carbon composites). Their Coefficient of Thermal Expansion (CTE)s are reported in Tab. 2. The mismatches in these values highlight why combining different material classes in a single high-temperature STT core is challenging: large CTE mismatches at joints and interfaces can produce substantial thermomechanical stresses during the repeated heating and cooling cycles shown in Figure 5.

3.1 Refractory metals

Refractory metals such as tungsten and molybdenum offer excellent high-temperature capability and high thermal conductivity, making them attractive for components exposed to high heat fluxes. Tungsten combines a very high melting point (3695 K) with good mechanical strength at elevated temperatures. However, these materials present some limitations. Their high density introduces a significant mass penalty, and their relatively low specific heat reduces their effectiveness as TES materials. In addition, interactions with carbon at high temperature can lead to carbide formation, potentially introducing brittle phases; nevertheless, these effects typically become significant only above the maximum operating temperature considered for this application [10].

From a manufacturing perspective, AM of refractory metals is typically achieved via powder-bed fusion techniques such as selective laser melting or electron beam melting. These processes enable the fabrication of complex geometries but are challenged by high melting temperatures, residual stresses, and crack formation. Recent research has demonstrated that alloying strategies and improved process control can significantly enhance the printability of tungsten and tungsten-based alloys, enabling crack-free structures in certain compositions [11]. Molybdenum is somewhat easier to process due to its lower melting point and improved ductility compared with tungsten [12]. However, similar challenges related to residual stresses and brittle fracture can still occur during additive manufacturing.

Overall, refractory metals are well-suited for high-heat-flux regions or early-stage prototyping, where their high-temperature capability and relatively higher AM maturity can be advantageous.

3.2 Ceramic materials

High-temperature ceramics provide an attractive alternative to refractory metals due to their low density, excellent thermal stability, and chemical inertness. Among them, Silicon Carbide (SiC) is a particularly promising candidate, combining relatively high thermal conductivity, good mechanical strength at elevated temperature, and compatibility with hydrogen environments [13]. SiC is also well-suited for thermal cycling due to its moderate coefficient of thermal expansion and resistance to thermal shock. Several AM approaches are available, including binder jetting with silicon infiltration, stereolithography, and polymer-derived ceramic processes ([14], [15]). These techniques enable complex geometries but require careful control of shrinkage and porosity. However, the printing capability of SiC is not yet at an industrial level, and further research is needed to make the overall curing process applicable to real-world scenarios. Moreover, studies have demonstrated that a protective material barrier—such as Boron Nitride (BN)—would be required for operating temperatures above 1670 K.

Other ceramics, such as alumina (Al_2O_3) and boron carbide (B_4C), can also be considered. Alumina offers excellent chemical stability but relatively low thermal conductivity. Its printability has been studied in recent years, leading to the development of the commercially available Alumina 4N resin for resin-based printing. This technological advancement makes it an extremely viable candidate for the preliminary test campaign, particularly for tests involving representative propellants such as helium and nitrogen. However, the presence of oxygen would make its coupling with high-temperature hydrogen challenging in a real case scenario. As an alternative, boron carbide is lightweight and temperature-resistant but brittle and less mature in AM processing; its high heat capacity makes it still an attractive candidate for TES applications.

3.3 Carbon-based materials

Carbon-based materials, such as graphite and carbon-carbon composites, offer low density, excellent thermal shock resistance, and very high temperature capability in vacuum. Their relatively high specific heat and thermal conductivity make them a valid option for TES applications.

However, their use in hydrogen environments is limited by chemical reactivity at elevated temperatures, which can lead to material degradation. This issue can be mitigated by applying protective coatings, such as SiC or BN layers deposited by Chemical Vapour Deposition (CVD). AM of carbon-based materials is typically indirect, involving the printing of polymer-derived precursors followed by pyrolysis and densification, and requires significant post-processing. Graphite is often considered a TES material due to its high specific heat and machinability.

3.4 Material selection considerations

As anticipated, no single material fully satisfies all the requirements of an integrated RAC with TES functionality. Ceramics generally offer higher specific heat but lower thermal conductivity, while refractory metals exhibit the opposite behaviour. Carbon-based materials provide a compromise but suffer from hydrogen compatibility issues. A high specific heat material such as graphite could be considered as a candidate in a hybrid AM–classical machining solution to maximise energy storage. In such a configuration, graphite would be used only in the core cavity and would not be in direct contact with the propellant. The AM-printed HEX would then be made of a high-conductivity, high-temperature-resistant material, coated if necessary to prevent hydrogen embrittlement. An external layer of low-conductivity material, such as a ceramic coated with a low-emissivity solution, could then be applied to minimise radiation losses. In this context, AM would still be crucial to enhance the HEX geometry.

Although material considerations suggest that hybrid architectures would ultimately be optimal, a single-material approach is adopted in this study to simplify manufacturing, avoid material coupling issues, and provide a clear assessment of AM capabilities. The thermophysical properties of the selected candidates are summarised in Tab. 2; graphite is included as a reference given its favourable TES properties, even though it is not selected as the primary candidate for a single-material printed STT.

4. CORE DESIGN

The candidate materials selection put the basis for the integrated design process. The proposed methodology is applicable to single-material RAC configurations and can be extended to hybrid solutions. The process starts with estimating the core mass based on TES requirements and the selected heat transfer strategy. This defines a baseline cylindrical geometry that, together with the cavity diameter derived from the concentrator coupling, provides the input for the HEX sizing. An external check loop verifies that the thruster's performance meets the requirements through a set of operational scenarios.

A helical HEX is initially adopted as a baseline configuration to estimate the main performance metrics and validate the design. This reference solution is then compared with more advanced geometries enabled by AM, such as lattice-based structures. Both configurations are designed to fit in the same volume, for a consistent comparison. Once the core sizing is validated and coupled with an insulation strategy, a simplified nozzle is attached to enable a preliminary performance assessment (Figure 5 shows an operational example). At this stage, it is crucial to stress that the presented HEX will not be optimised only based on the temperature requirements and pressure losses. This system will serve to homogeneously transfer the thermal energy stored in a given absorber to the propellant for the duration of the

longest firing time foreseen by the preliminary mission analysis for the RCS. A helical or TPMS-based HEX optimised to only meet the target temperature jump of the given propellant would have a completely different geometry and, eventually, a smaller radial and axial size.

4.1 Parabolic Concentrator

Solar thermal propulsion systems rely on concentrated solar radiation as the primary heat source. In this work, the concentrator is initially sized to match the TU Delft test facility capabilities in terms of light beam diameter, focal length and average intensity. Then, a cartridge heater delivering the same estimated power will be used for preliminary power-temperature correlations. This will provide the baseline dataset for assessing the actual optical power delivered by the high-power xenon lamp coupled with the concentrator, as foreseen for subsequent testing phases. Further optimisation for mission scenarios is left for future work. Figure 1 gives an idea of a real-case scenario application, underlying how impactful a change in the power requirements will be on the configuration of a satellite that implements the Green SWaP solution.

As a first design iteration, the primary optical element was defined as a paraboloidal concentrator with aperture diameter $d_c = 300$ mm and rim angle $\phi_r = 45^\circ$, selected according to classical design guidelines to maximize the concentration ratio [16]. A Monte Carlo ray-tracing model ($N = 10,000$ rays) was developed to evaluate the irradiance distribution at the focal plane, including the effects of manufacturing errors and pointing inaccuracies. Based on preliminary analyses, the required input power lies in the range of 200–400 W, depending on the selected TES material and insulation strategy.

Figure 1. Power delivered by a system of solar concentrators as a function of the number of mirrors and the dish diameter in LEO illumination conditions (Solar Flux $I = 1360 \text{ W/m}^2$).

The focal spot diameter is determined by the combined effect of the solar angular size θ_s and the mirror slope error θ_f :

$$d_f = \frac{d_c \sin(\theta_s + \theta_f)}{\sin \phi_r \cdot \cos(\theta_s + \phi_r + \theta_f)} \quad (1)$$

Figure 2 shows the implication of this equation, highlighting that manufacturing errors and alignment uncertainties significantly affect the delivered flux distribution. Based on external constraints and reasonable error envelopes, a cavity diameter of 10 mm is selected as a trade-off between optical coupling efficiency and system compactness. This reference diameter is shown in Figure 2 as a white dashed line, confirming that most of the concentrated power falls within that radius across a large manufacturing and beam alignment error range [17].

4.2 Cavity

The cavity is a key component of the RAC, acting both as the optical receiver and as the primary thermal absorber. Its geometry directly influences the core sizing, the HEX dimensions, and the overall thermal performance. Its internal shape must ensure high absorptance and uniform heat distribution to avoid local overheating. Simple cylindrical cavities are easy to manufacture but suffer from back-reflection losses and non-uniform heating. Improved geometries, such as spherical or pyramidal end-caps, can enhance flux redistribution and reduce re-radiation losses. An optimal design typically includes a slightly diverging section followed by a converging region, promoting multiple internal reflections and aligning reflected rays with the cavity walls [18]. These design choices strongly depend on the angular distribution of the incoming radiation and therefore on the concentrator characteristics in terms of d_c and ϕ_r mainly.

To further improve optical performance, a Compound Parabolic Concentrator (CPC) can be inte-

grated at the cavity entrance. The CPC acts as a secondary concentrator, collecting rays within a given acceptance angle and redirecting them toward the receiver. This element can be designed independently and potentially manufactured separately, allowing adaptation to different optical configurations.

The effective absorptance of the cavity α_{eff} is a metric often used to determine the cavity geometry optimisation, and can be estimated as [19]:

$$\alpha_{eff} \approx \frac{\alpha}{1 - (1 - \alpha)(1 - A_{ap}/A_{tot})} \quad (2)$$

where A_{ap} is the aperture area and A_{tot} is the total internal surface area, and α is the material absorptance. Increasing the cavity aspect ratio improves absorptance by promoting multiple reflections, but also increases mass and radiative losses. Future work would perform a design optimization based on ray tracing computational solvers to define the design parameters shown in Fig. 3.

From a manufacturing perspective, AM enables greater design freedom compared to traditional methods, allowing complex internal geometries and integrated features. Surface roughness, often considered a limitation of AM, can be beneficial in this context by enhancing light diffusion, although excessive roughness may lead to local hotspots. In the proposed monolithic design, the cavity is integrated within the core structure, with the surrounding material acting as both thermal storage and structural support for the HEX. This eliminates thermal interfaces and improves the continuity of heat transfer. In this application scenario, printability shall also

Figure 2. Irradiance distribution at the focal plane as given by Eq. 1. The white dashed circle indicates the aperture boundary. Top row (a–c): effect of decreasing mirror angular error ($\theta_f = 1.0, 0.5,$ and 0.01 deg, left to right) at a fixed solar half-angle of 2 deg. Bottom row (d–f): effect of increasing solar half-angle ($\theta_s = 4, 2,$ and 0.267 deg, left to right) at a fixed mirror angular error of 0.1 deg; the rightmost case corresponds to the nominal solar half-angle in LEO.

be considered. Sharp edges and steep inclination (above 45 deg) shall be avoided.

Figure 3. Conceptual cavity design parameters. ϕ_c and ϕ_t are the CPC entrance and exit diameter, while θ_1 and θ_2 are the entrance and cap inclinations.

For the present study, a simplified cylindrical cavity is adopted to reduce modelling complexity (see Figure 6), since no optical effects are being simulated at this stage. A constant wall-temperature boundary condition is applied in the simulations, so local geometric variations do not affect the preliminary results. The focus at this stage is therefore on defining the cavity diameter, the target wall temperature required to achieve the desired specific impulse, and the corresponding input power. All these parameters are not affected by local variations in the cavity shape, ensuring the validity of these results for subsequent iterations. More detailed optical–thermal coupling analyses will be addressed in future work to refine the cavity design.

4.3 TES Mass Sizing

Once a reasonable cavity diameter and geometry are established, the core mass and outer diameter can be sized. Overall, the design flow proceeds as follows. Starting from an initial geometry guess in terms of RAC diameter, length, and HEX performance parameters, the wall temperature required to meet the target specific impulse is determined. The corresponding RAC mass and geometry are then derived from the thermal energy to be stored in the system. This updated geometry feeds back into the wall temperature estimation, forming an iterative loop that uses the RAC size as the convergence metric.

The mass estimation approach introduced by Kennedy [20] is adopted as a baseline and extended via an iterative procedure that couples the HEX design with the RAC sizing. The total thermal power delivered to the propellant is:

$$\dot{Q}_{\text{prop}} = \dot{m} \bar{c}_{p,\text{prop}} (T_{p,\text{out}} - T_{p,\text{in}}) \quad (3)$$

and the total energy stored in the RAC and released during a single firing of duration t_b is:

$$Q_{\text{prop}} = \dot{Q}_{\text{prop}} t_b \quad (4)$$

Under the TES assumption, the solid core acts as a pure heat sink. The required RAC mass is estimated by:

$$m_{\text{RAC}} = \frac{Q_{\text{prop}}}{C (T_{w,0} - T_{w,f})} \quad (5)$$

where C is the RAC's specific heat, $T_{w,0}$ is the initial wall temperature at the start of firing and $T_{w,f}$ =

$T_{p,\text{out}}$ is assumed as a conservative lower bound. The inner wall temperature $T_{w,0}$ required to heat the hydrogen from $T_{p,\text{in}}$ to $T_{p,\text{out}}$ is found by integrating the first-law differential equation along the helical channels:

$$\dot{m} c_{p,\text{prop}} \frac{dT}{dz} = h P (T_w - T) \quad (6)$$

which, treating T_w as a uniform boundary condition, gives:

$$T_{p,\text{out}} = T_w - (T_w - T_{p,\text{in}}) \exp\left(-\frac{h P L_{\text{eq}}}{\dot{m} c_p}\right) \quad (7)$$

Equation (7) is inverted for T_w using a bisection algorithm. The convective coefficient h is first estimated from the literature and subsequently refined using the one-dimensional flow simulation described in Section 5.2. Starting from an initial geometry guess, the wall temperature and required mass are updated at each iteration until both the outer diameter and length converge to within a relative tolerance of 10^{-3} . The outer geometry is derived by selecting a length-to-diameter ratio $L/D = 1.4$, representing a trade-off between convective area and radiative losses.

The converged geometry is validated against a lumped two-node transient model of the regenerator. The solid core (thermal capacity $C_s = m_{\text{RAC}} C$) exchanges heat with the flowing gas (capacity rate $C_f = \dot{m} c_{p,\text{H}_2}$) through a conductance $UA = h A_{\text{wet}}$, where A_{wet} is the wetted area provided by the HEX. The heat exchanger effectiveness and the temporal evolution of the solid temperature are:

$$\varepsilon = 1 - \exp(-NTU), \quad NTU = \frac{UA}{C_f} \quad (8)$$

The temporal evolution of the solid temperature follows:

$$T_s(t) = T_{\text{in}} + (T_{w,0} - T_{\text{in}}) e^{-\alpha t}, \quad \alpha = \frac{C_f}{C_s} (1 - e^{-NTU}) \quad (9)$$

Consequently, the instantaneous outlet temperature of the gas can be computed as:

$$T_{\text{out}}(t) = T_{\text{in}} + \varepsilon (T_{w,0} - T_{\text{in}}) e^{-\alpha t} \quad (10)$$

The required initial solid temperature is the minimum value that guarantees $T_{\text{out}}(t) \geq T_{p,\text{out}}$ for all $t \in [0, t_b]$. This equation is solved iteratively for $T_{w,0}$ with a damped fixed-point scheme until convergence. A corrective mass factor of 15% is applied to account for structural elements and interfaces not captured by the solid core model.

Five candidate materials are evaluated using this method: SiC, graphite, B_4C , tungsten, and molybdenum. Their thermophysical properties and sizing results are listed in Tab. 2, with key input parameters summarised in Tab. 1. C emerges as the dominant factor in determining the required thermal mass, but the different material densities yield a final volume range that falls within an envelope of 30% of the

largest and smallest values. Estimated inner wall temperatures remain within a narrow 1273–1407 K range across all candidates, confirming that mass and volume budgets, rather than thermal feasibility, are the key discriminators at this stage, with ceramics offering the best overall compromise.

Table 1. Key input parameters for the RAC sizing.

Parameter	Symbol	Value
Target specific impulse	I_{sp}	500 s
Thrust	F	1 N
Firing duration	t_b	20 s
H ₂ mass flow rate	\dot{m}	0.2 g/s
H ₂ inlet temperature	$T_{p,in}$	300 K
H ₂ target outlet temperature	$T_{p,out}$	1100 K
Length-to-diameter ratio	L/D	1.4

5. THERMAL MODEL

Following the preliminary mass and geometry sizing described in Section 4.3, a higher-fidelity light thermal simulation is performed in MATLAB to validate the design and determine the required pre-heating power. The full thermal cycle of the thruster is decomposed into three sequential phases: (1) pre-heating of the RAC by the concentrator prior to firing, (2) propellant heating during the firing sequence, and (3) passive cooling of the core after the burn. The simulation is run for all five candidate materials listed in Tab. 2, and results are compared against the target outlet temperature $T_{p,out}$ and the material temperature limit T_{max} . The aim is to build a computationally inexpensive near-1D model to support future design iterations and to tailor it using both 3D simulations and experimental results.

The RAC wall is discretised into $n_l = 3$ concentric annular layers bounded by radii r_k ($k = 0, \dots, n_l$), uniformly spaced between the cavity inner radius and the outer radius. The effective material density is back-computed from the total wall mass as $\rho_s = m_{RAC} / [\pi L (r_{out}^2 - r_{in}^2)]$, so that $\sum_j \rho_s V_j = m_{RAC}$ exactly, where V_j is the volume of each layer. The three representative output temperatures — T_{inner} , T_{mid} , and T_{outer} — correspond to the innermost, central, and outermost layers respectively. Radial conduction between adjacent layers j and $j + 1$ is modelled using the cylindrical thermal resistance.

5.1 Phase 1: Pre-heating

Before firing, the RAC must be brought from ambient temperature T_{amb} to the required initial wall temperature $T_{w,0}$ by the solar concentrator. The available pre-heating window is one sunlit arc of the orbit, $t_{heat} = t_{\odot} \cdot n_{orb} = 1800$ s.

It is important to note that the energy required to bring the RAC to its target wall temperature (represented by the input power multiplied by the heating time) is, in general, different from the energy delivered to the propellant described in Eq. (4). Rather than deriving the input power from an extended orbital energy budget, a target temperature to be reached before each firing is defined; the required in-

put power is then computed as a function of heating time, material properties, and RAC geometry, with a feedback loop enforcing upper and lower temperature bounds to prevent material melting and ensure minimum performance requirements.

The transient temperature of each layer is governed by:

$$\rho_s V_j c_{p,s} \frac{dT_j}{dt} = Q_{cond,j} + Q_{src,j} \quad (11)$$

where $Q_{cond,j}$ is the net conductive exchange with neighbouring layers, and $Q_{src,j}$ is a source or sink term applied only to the boundary layers. The solar input power P_{in} is applied as a surface flux on the innermost layer ($j = 1$), while at the outer surface ($j = n_l$), heat is lost by radiation and external convection, while intermediate layer exchange heat only by conduction. Equation (11) is integrated explicitly in time with $N_1 = 50,000$ uniform steps over t_{heat} .

Since the thruster is designed for vacuum operation, h_{ext} is set to zero for the primary sizing. However, the model retains this parameter to allow direct comparison with ground test results obtained under atmospheric conditions, where convective losses at the outer surface play a significant role. Figure 4 illustrates how both the outer surface emissivity and the convective coefficient influence the required input power and the equilibrium temperature reached during pre-heating phase. These considerations are essential for sizing the experimental setup and assessing the feasibility of the ground validation campaign.

Figure 4. Required input power as a function of outer surface emissivity and convective heat transfer coefficient, for the nominal RAC geometry of 30x70 mm. Each dash type as a upper and lower value, one for $\epsilon = 0.1$ and one for $\epsilon = 0.9$. The coloured space in between is for all the intermediate emissivity values.

A first estimation of the required input power is obtained from the global energy balance:

$$P_{in} = \frac{m_{RAC} c_{p,s} (T_{w,0} - T_{amb})}{t_{heat}} + Q_{rad} + Q_{conv} \quad (12)$$

Since the thermal losses in Eq. (12) depend on the instantaneous wall temperature, which evolves dur-

Table 2. Thermophysical properties of the candidate TES materials and preliminary RAC mass and geometry sizing results [21].

Material	α ($\mu\text{m m}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$)	C ($\text{J kg}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$)	k ($\text{W m}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$)	ρ (kg m^{-3})	Mass (g)	Volume (mm^3)	T_{wall} (K)
Graphite	4.0	710	120	2300	233	101 145	1273
SiC	5.4	800	200	3 200	182	56 789	1353
B ₄ C	5.0	1050	70	2 520	131	51 989	1368
Tungsten	4.4	150	170	19 300	801	41 501	1407
Molybdenum	6.5	251	138	10 280	72	55 617	1357

ing the transient, this estimate is refined iteratively: the full transient simulation is run with the current P_{in} , the final inner wall temperature $T_{\text{inner}}(t_{\text{heat}})$ is compared against $T_{w,0}$, and P_{in} is adjusted by a fixed increment until $|T_{\text{inner}} - T_{w,0}| < 10$ K. The resulting power range for the baseline geometry is 200–400 W, consistent with the flux levels achievable with a 300 mm diameter solar concentrator.

5.2 Phase 2: Propellant Heating

The wall temperatures at the end of Phase 1 initialise the Phase 2 simulation. The propellant, hydrogen in this case, enters the helical channels at $T_{p,\text{in}} = 300$ K and is heated as it flows along the axial coordinate $z \in [0, L]$, discretised on a uniform grid. The gas temperature evolves along the channel according to:

$$\dot{m} c_{p,\text{H}_2} \frac{dT_p}{dz} = h \frac{A_{\text{wet}}}{L} (T_{\text{wall,helix}}(z) - T_p(z)) \quad (13)$$

where $T_{\text{wall,helix}}$ is the wall temperature at the helix radius, and A_{wet}/L is the heat transfer area per unit axial length. The gas density is updated at each node using the ideal-gas law.

The local convection coefficient is derived from the Nusselt number. For turbulent flow ($Re > 2300$), the Dittus–Boelter correlation provides the straight-tube baseline for the Nusselt Number Nu_0 . A curvature correction accounting for the secondary-flow (Dean-number) enhancement in helically coiled tubes is then applied:

$$h_{\text{turb}} = \frac{Nu_0 k_{\text{H}_2}}{D_i} \left(1 + 3.5 \frac{D_i}{D_h} \right) \quad (14)$$

For laminar flow ($Re \leq 2300$), the fully-developed Nusselt number $Nu = 4.36$ is corrected using the Dean number $De = Re \sqrt{D_i/(2R_h)}$:

$$h_{\text{lam}} = \frac{4.36 k_{\text{H}_2}}{D_i} (1 + 0.1 De^{0.5}) \quad (15)$$

Three operating modes are supported: (i) TES mode (zero solar input during firing, worst case), in which the wall cools as it transfers energy to the gas; (ii) constant wall temperature (primary sizing case), consistent with the heat-sink assumption used in the 3D simulations; and (iii) distributed heat source representing direct solar input. The coupled gas–wall system is solved at each axial node by a relaxation scheme ($\omega = 0.4$) until convergence.

The axial pressure field is computed simultaneously with the temperature field. The friction factor is evaluated using the Blasius correlation for turbulent

flow and the Hagen–Poiseuille result for laminar flow, both corrected for helical curvature via the Ito correction [22]. The pressure decrement at each axial step is:

$$\delta p = -\frac{f}{2} \rho_{\text{H}_2} u^2 \frac{\delta z}{D_i} \quad (16)$$

The total pressure drop is accumulated over all nodes, providing an additional feasibility constraint on the channel geometry alongside the thermal outlet temperature.

If $T_{\text{H}_2}(L)$ does not meet $T_{p,\text{out}}$ within 10 K, P_{in} is adjusted and Phase 1 is re-run with the updated power, feeding new initial wall temperatures into Phase 2. This outer loop continues until the target outlet temperature is met or the inner wall temperature exceeds T_{max} , at which point the material is flagged as thermally infeasible for the given geometry. An example of temperature distribution for the HEX described in Table 3 is shown in Figure 8.

5.3 Phase 3: Passive Cooling

After the firing, the RAC cools passively. The multi-layer radial model of Phase 1 is reused with the solar input removed, and initial conditions taken from the end of Phase 2. The governing equation for each layer remains Eq. (11) with:

$$Q_{\text{src},n_l} = -\varepsilon_{\text{ext}} \sigma A_{\text{out}} (T_{n_l}^4 - T_{\text{amb}}^4) - h_{\text{ext}} A_{\text{out}} (T_{n_l} - T_{\text{amb}}) \quad (17)$$

and $Q_{\text{src},j} = 0$ for all other layers. The simulation uses explicit time steps over t_{cool} . The cooling history determines the thermal state of the thruster at the start of the next firing cycle and bounds the temperature amplitude that drives fatigue in repeated LEO operations. The key parameters of all three phases are summarised in Table 3.

Table 3. Key parameters for the three-phase thermal simulation.

Parameter	Symbol	Value
Sunlit pre-heating window	t_{\odot}	60 min
Cooling duration	t_{cool}	30 min
Outer emissivity	ε_{ext}	0.2
Cavity absorptivity	α_c	0.9
Channel inner diameter	D_i	1.4 mm
Helix pitch	p	8 mm
Number of channels	N_t	4
Inlet pressure	p_{in}	6 bar
Radial wall layers	n_l	3
Phase 2 relaxation factor	ω	0.4

5.4 Orbital Operation Simulation

The three-phase model described above was applied to simulate a realistic multi-orbit operational scenario, using the converged RAC–helical HEX geometry as input. The purpose of this simulation is to verify that the design meets the expected performance requirements under representative RCS operating conditions, rather than the idealised single-cycle assumptions used for sizing. The simulation spans four consecutive LEO orbits, each composed of a 60-minute sunlight arc followed by a 30-minute eclipse. Four RCS firings of varying duration (5, 10, 20, and 15 s) are scheduled at different points in the orbital cycle, with some occurring during sunlight and others during an eclipse, in order to test both the pre-heating and the cooling states of the system. At each firing event, phase two is used to compute the hydrogen exit temperature and the resulting specific impulse using classical nozzle theory.

A feedback control loop regulates the pre-heating phase. During sunlight arcs, the input power is modulated to keep the inner wall temperature within prescribed upper and lower bounds ($T_{\text{lower}} = 800$ K and $T_{\text{upper}} = 1400$ K). When the wall temperature reaches the upper bound, the heater is switched off; it is reactivated once the temperature drops below the lower bound. An insulation layer is wrapped around the outer surface of the RAC and is included in the simulation through its thickness, thermal conductivity, and surface emissivity. The detailed design of this layer is beyond the scope of the present work; the values adopted here (summarised in Table 3) are representative of commercially available high-temperature insulation solutions and are used to provide realistic boundary conditions for the orbital simulation. The sensitivity of the pre-heating power to these parameters is illustrated in Figure 4, and will be used for the insulation design in future work.

The simulation output confirms that, across all four orbits and all scheduled firing events, the inner wall temperature remains within the selected limits and the propellant exit temperature consistently exceeds the threshold required to achieve the target specific impulse of 500 s. The results also demonstrate that the feedback controller is able to recover the required thermal state within a single orbit following an eclipse firing, even in the most demanding case of a 20 s burn occurring shortly after the start of the eclipse. An example of the output of a feedback control algorithm is shown in Figure 5.

6. 3D SIMULATION

As mentioned in Section 3, Tungsten is selected as the baseline material for the HEX CFD simulations. Although it is not the optimal TES candidate due to its high density and relatively low specific heat, the maturity of tungsten AM processes and its well-established compatibility with hydrogen make it the most suitable choice for a first prototype intended to undergo a complete validation campaign (from additive manufacturing qualification through thermal

testing, concentrator coupling, and thruster characterisation) without requiring protective coatings for hydrogen compatibility or novel processing routes for the operational temperature range considered. A second prototype, incorporating higher-performing materials optimised for TES capacity, will follow once the geometry and manufacturing approach have been validated. Last but not least, this material would eventually enable an operational range extension thanks to its extremely high melting point, making it a valuable candidate for a future high-performance prototype.

The simulation targets a core volume of approximately $40,000 \text{ mm}^3$, as reported in Tab. 2, with a total thruster envelope of $50,000 \text{ mm}^3$ that allocates 25% of the volume to the nozzle, chamber, inlet, and plenum regions. Figure 6 shows the geometry used for the HEX comparison. The helical channel parameters were determined using the MATLAB sizing model, and the volume they require was then filled with a diamond TPMS lattice to generate the alternative configuration. Among the lattice architectures evaluated for heat exchange in small thrusters, the diamond TPMS has been shown to offer the most effective balance of surface area and pressure loss [23]. TPMS structures maximise the heat transfer area per unit volume, generate a near-symmetric thermal contact surface that permits thinner walls, and are inherently self-supporting during printing, which makes them well suited to AM. They also isolate two distinct fluid regions (a hot and a cold side) making them natural candidates for counter-flow HEX applications, although this property is not specifically exploited in the present single-fluid configuration. In this first design iteration, the lattice parameters were set by trial and error. Future work will apply simulation-driven optimisation to tune the cell size, aspect ratio, and mid-surface offset in order to maximise thermal performance while controlling pressure losses. Figure 7 shows the two resulting fluid domains.

6.1 Simulation Setup

A density-based solver was adopted to handle the compressibility effects, equation-of-state coupling, and transonic flow conditions associated with high-temperature, low-density hydrogen expanding through a converging–diverging nozzle. A pressure-based solver is less suited to these conditions due to its difficulty in handling strong compressibility and shock waves.

An extended downstream fluid domain (i.e. a large vacuum region beyond the nozzle exit that allows the plume to expand freely and reach the correct pressure matching with the ambient) was not included in order to limit the cell count and computational cost. Instead, pressure inlet and outlet boundary conditions were applied directly at the domain boundaries, and the parameters were iteratively refined until choked conditions were achieved at the throat. The resulting mass flow rate was within 15% of the design value for both configurations, which is considered

representative of the intended operating point.

The choked throat condition is the key justification for this simplification: once the flow is sonic at the throat, conditions upstream of it are completely decoupled from the downstream pressure field. Consequently, the heat transfer and flow behaviour inside the HEX (which lie upstream of the throat) are not affected by the absence of an extended domain. Quantities that depend on the correct downstream pressure matching, such as thrust, nozzle efficiency, and specific impulse in strongly over- or under-expanded conditions, cannot be evaluated reliably from this setup and are therefore not reported here.

6.2 CFD Results and Discussion

Figure 9 and Figure 10 show the resulting temperature and pressure distributions for both HEX configurations. The temperature field in the helical HEX shows that the propellant reaches thermal equilibrium with the wall within the first few turns of the channel. This result should be understood in the context of the simulation assumptions: a steady-state simulation with a constant wall temperature of 1400 K represents the best-case thermal scenario, in which the wall is always available at its peak temperature and the propellant therefore heats up faster than in a real firing. The sizing procedure was intentionally built around the worst case, producing a conservative geometry. The two analyses are complementary and both necessary: the sizing model defines a safe design envelope, while the steady-state CFD confirms that nominal performance requirements are met once steady state is reached.

In a physically realistic transient firing, the wall temperature decreases continuously as the solid core transfers energy to the propellant. The MATLAB model of Section 5 captures this behaviour more faithfully by propagating the wall temperature forward in time under actual energy extraction conditions, and is therefore more appropriate for estimating end-of-burn performance. The CFD results serve as an essential validation anchor for this analytical model:

the MATLAB model was re-run with an inlet temperature of 1300 K (consistent with the CFD finding that hydrogen reaches approximately 1300 K before entering the helical channels due to direct radiative and conductive heating in the inlet region) and the resulting temperature profile along the HEX is in close agreement with the CFD prediction (see Figure 8, providing additional confidence in the analytical model). The inlet heating also produces steep local temperature gradients that risk non-uniform heating, thermomechanical stress concentrations, and accelerated material fatigue, making inlet geometry optimisation a priority for the next design iteration.

The helical HEX shows a slightly higher outlet temperature (30 K) than the TPMS solution under the current meshing approach, but this difference should not be taken as evidence that the TPMS is thermally inferior. On the contrary, TPMS structures inherently generate localised flow disturbances near the wall that enhance the local convective heat transfer coefficient — an effect that requires a refined boundary layer mesh along the complex lattice surfaces to be captured accurately. This refinement was not applied in the present first campaign, meaning the TPMS thermal performance is underestimated at this stage. Mesh refinement is expected to bring its outlet temperature closer to, or above, that of the helical solution.

Where the TPMS architecture already demonstrates a clear advantage is in pressure drop. It exhibits near-zero pressure loss in the present configuration, while the helical HEX produces a total pressure drop of 0.36 bar — approximately 27% above the analytical estimate of Eq. (16). This result confirms the intrinsic superiority of TPMS lattices for low-loss heat exchange, even before any geometry optimisation has been applied.

The present steady-state simulation comprised more than 20 million cells and required over 10 hours to converge. A transient simulation was subsequently initiated from the converged solution; after 32 hours

Figure 5. Simulated orbital thermal cycle of the RAC over four consecutive orbits, showing the inner wall temperature (solid line) and outer surface temperature (dashed line) alongside the feedback control bounds and scheduled RCS firing events (green markers). Background shading indicates the orbital phase: yellow (heater on), red (heater off), and blue (eclipse).

Figure 6. A section of the STT model used for the helical and TPMS HEX comparison, showing the HEX region in light blue.

of wall-clock time, only 10^{-5} physical seconds had been advanced. Rather than indicating that transient simulation is unnecessary, this demonstrates that meaningful transient results demand time-stepping optimisation strategies — such as adaptive stepping or implicit solvers — that are beyond the scope of this work but are essential for the next phase.

A fully representative validation requires a 20-second transient simulation incorporating a turbulence model capable of resolving the boundary layer, an orbital radiation environment, and an extended downstream domain, starting from the converged wall temperature and evolving freely under the imposed conditions. Due to the three-dimensional and time-dependent behaviour of the TPMS structure, symmetry or domain decomposition simplifications are not appropriate for this phase. These requirements define the scope of the planned next-phase simulation campaign, which will be coupled with the experimental test programme.

7. CONCLUSIONS

This work has presented an integrated design approach for a solar thermal thruster core combining a RAC, TES, and HEX in a single-material, additively manufactured component. Starting from the mission requirements, a numerical model was developed to select candidate materials, size the RAC–HEX system, and validate the design through thermal and CFD simulations. The thermal model demonstrated that the presented RAC configuration meets the target specific impulse of 500 s across the representative orbital operating conditions, including eclipse firings and feedback-controlled pre-heating cycles.

The CFD comparison between the helical and diamond TPMS HEX configurations confirms the potential of AM-enabled lattice geometries. The TPMS solution exhibits near-zero pressure losses compared to the helical design, while delivering competitive

Figure 7. Fluid domains inside the helical (a) and TPMS (b) HEX configurations.

Figure 8. Temperature distribution along the helical channel computed by the Phase 2 model for the baseline tungsten geometry, using the same inlet condition extrapolated from the CFD analysis.

Figure 9. Fluid temperature contour at the wall interface for the helical (left) and TPMS (right) configurations.

thermal performance even without boundary layer mesh refinement or geometry optimisation. Field-driven topology optimisation, combined with a refined meshing strategy, is expected to further improve its heat transfer performance and fully exploit the geometric freedom offered by AM. Both configurations confirm that the proposed design meets nominal performance requirements under steady-state conditions.

Future work will focus on three fronts. First, a test campaign will validate the printed geometries and characterise manufacturing tolerances for both tungsten and candidate high-temperature materials. Second, a transient CFD simulation incorporating turbulence modelling and a realistic radiation environment will provide a more rigorous performance assessment, with particular attention to inlet design and TPMS boundary layer behaviour. Third, a second-generation prototype incorporating a higher-performing TES material will be designed based on the validated geometry, with the aim of demonstrating the full integrated functionality of the RAC–HEX core under representative solar input conditions. Collectively, this work contributes to the broader roadmap for high-efficiency, additively manufactured solar ther-

mal propulsion systems suitable for green, reusable in-space applications.

Figure 10. Fluid pressure contour at the wall interface for the helical (left) and TPMS (right) configurations.

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